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IS PERSONALITY THE MISSING KEY FOR BOOSTING SALES? A FRESH PERSPECTIVE FOR MARKETING STRATEGISTS ON SERBIAN CONSUMERS' ORGANIC FOOD ATTITUDES

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Abstract: *The consumers of today are adopting new food preferences, one of them being a growing inclination towards buying organic food. Nonetheless, the organic food sector of the Republic of Serbia has yet to reach its full potential – an adequate marketing and economic strategy is required to achieve tangible results in this field and educate consumers about the benefits of organic food. In light of that, this paper aims to provide exactly the foundation for such a plan – beginning with administering a 3-part questionnaire (demographics, Big Five and attitudes towards organic food) to a sample of adult Serbian citizens (N = 504). Pearson's correlation was done for statistical analysis, wherein it was found that Openness to Experience and Agreeableness were significantly positively associated with attitudes towards organic food, which was consistent with some of the hypotheses made on the basis of previous studies. These results point to conclusions that provide fresh implications for a more successful promotion of organic food within Serbia, based on tailoring advertisements and national marketing campaigns to specific personality traits, in order to increase sales.*

Keywords: Organic food, Big Five, Marketing, Consumer Attitudes, Personality

1. INTRODUCTION

The needs of today's consumers – the majority of whom strive to have access to food of appropriate quality – are growing increasingly complex. Modern consumers have developed new habits when it comes to diets and nutrition, which has led to the consumption of organic agricultural products becoming more frequent. The economic sector of organic food products has experienced significant development at the global level, in light of the expressed awareness of people about the importance of consuming organic food and the rise of demand for natural products (that is, those that do not contain pesticides, chemicals and genetic modifications) [1].

However, the Serbian organic food sector is not large and is rather poorly developed; therefore, it can be classified as an emerging market. The main challenge it faces is that the largest share of production is exported in the form of raw materials, whilst the most significant share is imported as a finished product. In this way, a vast portion of the profit is transferred to foreign economies. It is estimated that a total of 1% of organically produced food is sold on the domestic market [2]. In order to have a positive impact on this state of the market, it is necessary to devise a proper marketing plan and put it together in accordance with consumer habits, and one of the best ways to do this is precisely through the analysis of their attitudes and personality traits.

The aim of this paper is to explore whether the fundamental personality traits (namely, the Big 5 personality traits), such as Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness and Neuroticism, play a role in consumer attitudes towards the production and consumption of organic food in Serbia. Based on previous literature on the topic, it can be hypothesized that a link

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will be found. More specifically, past research has established a connection between willingness to buy organic food and Big 5 personality traits [3]. For instance, one study found a positive association with Agreeableness and Openness to Experience, no link with Neuroticism and Conscientiousness and negative association with Extraversion [4]. Understanding such relationships can help with developing a better segmentation of the organic food market, as well as in creating more effective strategies for promotion and educating consumers about the benefits of this way of food production.

2. THE STUDY

2.1 Materials and Methods

The data was collected online, that is, by means of a questionnaire (fully in Serbian language) created in Google Forms format. The questionnaire consists of three basic parts: socio-demographic questions, globally recognized abbreviated version of the questionnaire for the Big 5 personality traits (BFI 10 Serbian version) [5] and a specially created part related to attitudes towards organic food production in Serbia. The survey was completely anonymous, and the collected data was used exclusively for research purposes. The research was carried out in the period July-August 2025, and the responses were given by a sample of 504 adult citizens of the Republic of Serbia.

When it comes to statistical analysis, Pearson's correlation was used to find links between personality and attitudes towards organic food. Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated in Jamovi Statistical Software.

2.2 Results

The demographics of the sample are diverse. In terms of biological sex, 246 of the respondents were male, whilst 258 of the respondents were female, amounting to 48.8% and 51.2%, respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Sample structure with regard to the biological sex of the respondents
Source: Author

As for the age, educational background, employment status and previous knowledge of the topic of food production, most participants were in the 18 to 25 age range (23.4%), held a Bachelor's degree

(43.5%), were employed (64.7%) and were partially familiarized with food production during their previous schooling (34.7%).

The survey also contained a question about consumers' motives to purchase organic food. The most frequently cited motive to buy organic food was Health concerns and disease prevention. Figure 2 shows the sample structure of the respondents in relation to their stated motives to purchase organic food.

Figure 2 Sample structure with regard to the motives to buy organic food
Source: Author

Neuroticism and attitudes towards organic food were found to be positively associated; albeit, the correlation was weak and insignificant ($r = 0.074$, $p = 0.098$). The correlation matrix for this statistical relationship is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Correlation matrix for the link between Neuroticism and attitudes towards organic food
Source: Jamovi 2.3.28 statistical software

		NEUROTICISM
ATTITUDES TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD	Pearson's r	0.074
	df	502
	p-value	0.098

Note. H_a is positive correlation

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, one-tailed

A significant positive correlation was determined between attitudes towards organic food and Extraversion ($r = 0.177$, $p < 0.001$). In other words, this means that the more extraverted an individual is, the more likely they are to hold a favourable attitude towards organic food. Table 2 shows the correlation matrix for this statistical relationship.

Table 2. Correlation matrix for the link between Extraversion and attitudes towards organic food
Source: Jamovi 2.3.28 statistical software

		EXTRAVERSION	
ATTITUDES TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD	Pearson's r	0.177	***
	df	502	
	p-value	< .001	

Note. H_a is positive correlation

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, one-tailed

A significant positive association was found between attitudes towards organic food and Openness to Experience ($r = 0.155$, $p < 0.001$). This implies that individuals who are driven by curiosity and are keen for new experiences are also more likely to have a better view about organic food. Table 3 presents the correlation matrix for this link.

Table 3. Correlation matrix for the link between Openness to Experience and attitudes towards organic food
Source: Jamovi 2.3.28 statistical software

		OPENNESS TO EXPERIENCE	
ATTITUDES TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD	Pearson's r	0.155	***
	df	502	
	p-value	< .001	

Note. H_a is positive correlation

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, one-tailed

Higher Agreeableness scores were linked with more positive attitudes towards organic food ($r = 0.154$). The correlation found was significant ($p < 0.001$). Table 4 shows the correlation matrix for this association.

Table 4. Correlation matrix for the link between Agreeableness and attitudes towards organic food
Source: Jamovi 2.3.28 statistical software

		AGREEABLENESS	
ATTITUDES TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD	Pearson's r	0.154	***
	df	502	
	p-value	< .001	

Note. H_a is positive correlation

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, one-tailed

An insignificant negative correlation was present between Conscientiousness and attitudes towards organic food ($r = -0.141$, $p = 0.999$). In other words, although this would mean that conscientious individuals are less inclined to view organic food favorably, this statistical relationship is likely due to random chance (Table 5).

Table 5. Correlation matrix for the link between Conscientiousness and attitudes towards organic food

Source: *Jamovi 2.3.28 statistical software*

			CONSCIENTIOUSNESS	
ATTITUDES TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD			Pearson's r	-0.141
			df	502
			p-value	0.999

Note. H_a is positive correlation

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, one-tailed

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The most notable results from this paper (which support part of the hypotheses made) include a significant positive correlation between attitudes towards organic food, as well as Agreeableness and Openness to Experience. This is also consistent with data from previous psychological studies, which have linked environmental concern (often seen as a key component of increased awareness about organic food) with these two personality traits [6,7,8].

More specifically, Openness to Experience is related to higher cognitive ability, which is linked to environmentally conscious behaviour [9,10]. Moreover, individuals high in Openness to Experience tend to be more receptive to something new, which implies that they are more willing to engage in habits that they believe are sustainable – including buying organic food. Individuals who are open to experiences may be more concerned about the aesthetic elements of life and nature in general in contrast to those individuals who score low in Openness to Experience [4].

Similarly, individuals who are agreeable are also more compassionate, whereas individuals who are less agreeable are more inclined to be self-centred and antisocial [10]. Furthermore, the positive association between Agreeableness and environmental concern is in line with findings which demonstrate that altruism is amongst the main elements of pro-environmental views [4].

As expected, there was no meaningful statistical relationship between attitudes towards organic food and the traits of Neuroticism and Conscientiousness. However, it is important to note that the finding for Conscientiousness is partially inconsistent (even though negative, its correlation is not significant) with one study from Norway which found a significant negative association between this trait and willingness to purchase organic food (WTP). As that study explains though, the factor causing the low WTP among conscientious Norwegians may lie in the fact that Norwegian small-scale farming is highly focused on plant and animal health. This means that the Norwegian population, unlike their Serbian counterparts, does not notice too much of a difference between organic food and ordinary food. That makes it possible that individuals high in Conscientiousness may be more conscious of that than individuals who score low on this particular trait [11].

Contrary to the hypothesis, Extraversion was significantly positively associated with attitudes towards organic food. This might mean that outgoing, lively and sociable individuals are of the

opinion that organic food tastes better, and therefore have a higher likelihood of buying it. One explanation for this result is that there are certain traits or values that are positively associated with Extraversion and negatively associated with organic food views, or vice versa.

However, it is difficult to speak about a direct causal link between personality and attitudes of organic food. There may be mediators (or in other words, third variables) in this relationship. Indeed, there may be completely different reasons for the obtained results, such as, for example, moral values of the respondents.

One recommendation for future research is to conduct a longitudinal study (one taking place over a longer period of time) with an even larger sample size for higher statistical power. This would involve investing in marketing studies aimed at the Serbian market, where, through targeted surveys of a representative sample of the Serbian population, research could be conducted on the motives, personal values and attitudes towards purchasing organic food in Serbia and its connections to personality traits. In order to strengthen international cooperation and global recognition of local companies within this sector, this would gain further relevance by turning into a cross-national comparative study where participants from multiple countries would participate. If such studies bring consistently similar results, it would be beneficial to also consider funding educational programs designed with the nuances of the Big 5 personality traits in mind. This should be balanced with convincing, evidence-based arguments (paired with laboratory testing to confirm the quality of organic food to the majority of the population who stated that health concerns are their main motive to buy it), in order to change dietary habits and switch to organic food. All of this would allow for better adjustment of branding strategies for companies in this sector and enable them to not only increase their profit through enhanced sales of their products but also contribute to the overall higher-quality, healthier, and better diet of the citizens of the Republic of Serbia.

LITERATURE

- [1] Duram, Leslie A.. "organic food". *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 29 Apr. 2025, Available on: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/organic-food> (Accessed: 20.09.2025.)
- [2] Sredojević, Z., Oljača, S., (2018): Efikasnost organske proizvodnje – malina, višnja, paprika, Univerzitet u Beogradu – Poljoprivredni fakultet, page. 20
- [3] Bazzani, Claudia, Caputo, Vincenzina, Nayga, Rodolfo M., Canavari, Maurizio, Revisiting consumers' valuation for local versus organic food using a non-hypothetical choice experiment: Does personality matter?, *Food Quality and Preference*, Volume 62, 2017, Pages 144-154, ISSN 0950-3293
- [4] Gustavsen, Geir Wæhler, Hegnes, Atle Wehn, Individuals' personality and consumption of organic food, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 245, 2020, 118772, ISSN 0959-6526
- [5] Pejić, M., Tenjović, L., & Knežević, G. (2014). Validation of the BFI-10 questionnaire – Short Version of the Big Five Inventory, *Primenjena Psihologija*, 7(1), 45–92.
- [6] Hirsh, Jacob B., Personality and environmental concern, *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Volume 30, Issue 2, 2010, Pages 245-248, ISSN 0272-4944
- [7] Milfront, Taciano L., Sibley, Chris G., The big five personality traits and environmental engagement: Associations at the individual and societal level, *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Volume 32, Issue 2, 2012, Pages 187-195, ISSN 0272-4944,
- [8] Nisbet, E. K., Zelenski, J. M., & Murphy, S. A. (2008). The Nature Relatedness Scale: Linking Individuals' Connection With Nature to Environmental Concern and Behavior. *Environment and Behavior*, 41(5), 715-740.
- [9] DeYoung, C. G., Peterson, J. B., & Higgins, D. M. (2005). Sources of openness/intellect: Cognitive and neuropsychological correlates of the fifth factor of personality. *Journal of personality*, 73(4), 825-858.
- [10] Hirsh, Jacob B., Environmental sustainability and national personality, *Journal of Environmental Psychology*. Volume 38, 2014, Pages 233-240, ISSN 0272-4944,
- [11] Kvakkestad, V., Berglann, H., Refsgaard, K., & Flaten, O. (2018). Citizen and consumer evaluation of organic food and farming in Norway. *Organic Agriculture*, 8(2), 87-103.